

KT4D

Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

Risks to individual freedoms of speech and action

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable, first submitted in M12 as v1, provides a conceptual overview of some of the problems AI and big data pose to democracy from an institutional perspective. Module D focuses on the use of personal data and user profiling. Module E focuses on the control of individual speech and action. This version builds on v2 to begin to provide a toolkit to advance the state of the art in these two domains.

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2 Potential Risks to Individual Freedoms

Since our liberal democracies generally employ forms of representativeness to their institutions, the impact of AI on free and fair elections is also one of the key ways in which technology affects our politics. The level of acceptance of the results from the elections - the legitimacy of the outcome - rests largely on how those who end up with less power shares in the representative system see the fairness of the election process itself. This includes the ability of individuals and groups to express their views freely, having access to information, and forming an informed opinion of the capabilities and views of candidates and parties. The EU Commission launched a study to map the issue in a recent report (Trasys International, 2021), and academic literature also indicates different ways AI can be used to influence free and fair elections. The key dimensions include: job displacement and economic inequality, privacy and surveillance, disinformation, and voter manipulation and suppression.

2.1 Job Displacement and Economic Inequality

The rapid advancement of AI and its applications in various domains has raised concerns about the impact of automation on the future of work. One of the main issues is the potential displacement of human workers by AI systems, especially in white collar jobs that require cognitive and analytical skills. These jobs were previously thought to be immune to automation, but recent studies have indicated that many of them are susceptible to being replaced or augmented by AI (Eloundou et al. 2023). This has been seen perhaps most acutely with the negative effects of generative AI on artists and writers. These effects could lead to significant changes in the labour market, such as job losses, skill mismatches, wage polarisation, and income inequality. Others emphasise the potential for new job creation and the need for skill adaptation in response to technological advancements (Autor 2015; Brynjolfsson & McAfee 2014). It is also worth noting AI can impact workers within the workplace through algorithmic management, surveillance and incentivization of productivity in order to shift risks from firms to workers (Moradi & Levy 2020). The widening scope of such labour market effects intensifies the spectre of economic inequality, contributing to socio-economic disparities and unrest that directly impinges upon democratic stability.

2.2 The Effects of AI and the Law

Because of the varying ways that AI and big data can be utilised to make predictions, its use in courts, criminal proceedings and law enforcement is growing. This section explores some of the risks AI and big data can pose to the lives of citizens in aspects such as micro-criminality, civil disobedience, and predicting criminality.

2.2.1 Extensive Punishment and Micro-Criminality

Almost $\frac{3}{4}$ of individuals in Britain admit to having committed some minor crime (Dean, 2016). With the rise of surveillance technology, tracking us and collecting information about our activities, we might seriously constrain our freedom (Manheim and Kaplan, 2019: 126; Susskind, 2018: 172). If for

example one wishes to chance not getting a TV licence, it may be significantly harder to do so when your TV can notify the authorities immediately. In other examples surveillance itself is not required, we can imagine an algorithm within a self-driving vehicle that simply doesn't allow you to exceed speed limits. Whilst this on the face of it seems to be a positive, after all, we want people to adhere to the law, we lose the ability to break it even to a minor degree (thus constraining one's autonomy). This is of particular importance in democracies when we think about the notion of civil disobedience.

2.2.2 Civil Disobedience

Civil disobedience is an act of resistance in the name of a cause of social justice. Previous examples of movements like these include women's suffrage, LGBT protests (such as Stonewall) and the black civil rights movement. Freedom to do these acts in democracy is often defended by political theorists. Rawls (2004) for example believed that even in politically liberal democratic societies, it is still possible that unjust laws can be created. We therefore ought to uphold a right to civil disobedience for the purposes of bringing about a more just society. Importantly, this must be done in a non-violent manner, with a good chance of success. The participants must also do so publicly and non-evasively (Rawls, 2004: 367).

It is not hard to see how AI and big data could improve our ability to perform acts of civil disobedience, or at least given further means by which it can be done. The advent of 'hactivist groups' such as Anonymous, who can attack government systems or infiltrate data banks, in the name of a cause may provide some evidence for this (Himma, 2007: 73; Wyant, 2012). Rawls (2004) may object to the anonymity of these groups, since in being evasive they could be perceived as calling into question the legitimacy of the institutions themselves: one ought to accept the consequences of one's actions to display what is sometimes called 'fidelity to law', to show one's acts are calls for change rather than revolution. Though it is not immediately apparent why 'fidelity to law' is the only method by which one can communicate that an act of civil disobedience is non-revolutionary. This is especially poignant when we consider our modern context, wherein all one has to do to get a message out into the world is tweet.¹ Perhaps something like 'it was me! Let's change this unjust system (but don't overthrow the government)'. Seemingly if the non-revolutionary message can be carried out regardless, we have no need for the non-evasion condition.

Although, we should also consider potential responses to this change in activism. For example, social media platforms now use encryption (encoding messages) to make hacking difficult. A consequence of this is also that it makes government surveillance on privately owned platforms more difficult (Clark, 2017; Corera, 2017). This sort of surveillance is not alien to democracies, as was exposed in the case of Edward Snowden, who leaked information that the NSA had been illegally spying on private citizens (Casciani, 2018). The increased security of private platforms has given states cause to make their own online platforms that can be surveyed more easily. WeChat in China is perhaps the best example of this, though other countries such as Turkey have also made new platforms such as their own national emailing system (Susskind, 2018: 183).

¹ Objections may be raised that algorithmic bias may mean your message is not heard. This is explored more fully in section 2.5.3.

Governments can also use algorithms themselves to monitor their citizens, such as China's social credit system (Qiang, 2019: 59 – 61). As a result of this, the presence of AI and big data may make acts of civil disobedience significantly harder to organise and carry out. Especially if a government makes their own national messaging systems like that in China (WeChat (Sonnad, 2017)). Supposing for example that one wishes to organise a protest, perhaps glueing oneself to the M4 motorway. You're in groups on Facebook with other like minded individuals, all of whom have phones with location tracking software. A message is sent out to the group specifying that the protest is today, but the government targets specific words, preventing any message containing these words from being received. Perhaps somehow you find out anyway, and continue to the location, you recognise your phone could be used to track you, so you discard it. As you walk along the street, you're continually noticed by surveillance cameras, who recognise your face as being within a group known for protests of this sort. Several other individuals from your group are also spotted heading towards a similar point from several directions. Feeding this information to an AI algorithm, it calculates there is a high possibility that you and your colleagues are attempting a protest. It therefore triangulates the location to which you are all headed, and authorities are on the scene before you even arrive (Susskind, 2018). This is a scary thought. It is scary because often those changes most integral to the flourishing of liberal democratic systems are those changes brought about by acts of civil disobedience. The prospect of this freedom being curtailed or highly limited in a world of AI and big data is thus highly alarming, if we suppose that any of our current laws and social structures are unjust in a similar manner to the issues highlighted by social justice movements prior. Since it would be incredibly contentious at best to suppose society as it stands has nothing more to learn, the introduction of these systems not only risks a curtailment of freedom, but the real possibility of tyranny.

2.2.3 Predicting Criminality

A potential limit to freedom is the use of AI in determining our activity, which in turn could affect how others treat us within society. For example, there are now machine learning algorithms that have been able to predict criminality simply by looking at someone's face, with 90% accuracy (Arcas et al, 2017; Wu et al, 2016: 3). Others can use sociological, or socioeconomic factors to predict areas of criminality, for the allocation of law enforcement resources (Castelli et al, 2017). If these factors can be used as predictors of activity, then a few things result: (1) our activity is far less determined by us than we originally thought (Susskind: 2018: 176), and/or (2) the state having access to this information can further exacerbate structural issues within law enforcement.

2.3 Voter Manipulation and Suppression

AI can largely influence the self-rule of the *demos* through shaping the information environments in different ways (Jungherr 2023). As a distinct dimension affecting free and fair elections, AI can be used to target and manipulate voters. By analysing vast amounts of data, AI systems can identify specific demographics and target them with tailored messages to shape their views and behaviour. This micro-targeting can potentially lead to manipulation, undermining the integrity of electoral processes (Jungherr 2023). Different ways of manipulation are still at the projection phase, which means some of the concrete impacts still remain to be seen and depend also on the level of technology in question. Noorman and Swierstra (2023) make a distinction between how AI can affect recognizing, resisting,

deliberating, voting, representing, joining, and exiting within democracies. The use of profiling as part of these tools is discussed in Module D.

2.4 Privacy and Surveillance

AI systems can collect and analyse large amounts of personal information from various sources, such as social media, online platforms, and biometric devices. This data can be used to profile, target, manipulate, or influence voters, as well as to monitor and suppress dissent (Coeckelbergh 2022b). Unauthorised access to personal data by hackers, foreign actors, or malicious insiders can compromise the security and integrity of elections, as well as expose sensitive information about individuals' preferences, opinions, and behaviours. Moreover, the use of surveillance technologies, such as facial recognition, drones, and smart cameras, can erode privacy and civil liberties, creating a chilling effect on democratic participation and free expression. As AI becomes more ubiquitous and powerful, the protection of privacy and surveillance becomes a crucial issue for ensuring the legitimacy and fairness of elections (Privacy International 2019).

In a world of increasing surveillance, whoever controls the technology (and the access to the data it provides) will have an enormous amount of power (Susskind, 2018: 124). In one respect this could create better people, since individuals behave differently when they know they're being observed, on the other hand this could put vast amounts of power in the hands of the government and would make the goals of a tyrannical government very easy.

2.5 Access and Evaluation of Information

AI algorithms on digital media platforms owned by private companies are now in a new and powerful position. They govern what type of deliberation is permissible, who it is seen by, and when. In effect this means AI algorithms owned by private companies are continuously regulating our ability to deliberate. This results in several issues for the value of freedom in democracy with respect to deliberation, but also several advantages.

First, the internet provides us with a great deal of information and may be a large forum by which deliberation can be done on a wide scale.² These platforms can be used to enhance deliberation, not merely in the public sphere, but with potential for implementation through online digital assemblies. However, in no way does this mean the deliberation is of good quality. Resulting from total anonymity, 'online trolls' – lacking face-to-face interaction and individual accountability – make good faith deliberation ever more difficult (Bartlett, 2018: Ch 1; Manheim and Kaplan, 2019: 127 – 128). AI-assisted algorithms, with their focus on engagement, can also make deliberation difficult.

Moreover, since these platforms offer lower accountability (because discussion can be anonymous) a greater diversity of discussions can occur without the issues of social taboo. Additionally, these platforms, in theory, give louder voices to minority groups and allow them to congregate in online spaces; finding each other and presenting their opinions to the wider public as a collective. Many social justice movements now heavily rely on online platforms and utilise the algorithms that spread

² This is explored further in module D.

information to present new points of discussion. These risks of AI to our epistemic freedoms are discussed below under the themes of epistemically assisting freedom (2.5.1), risks to the quality of information (2.5.2) and risks to the quality of discourse (2.5.3).

2.5.1 Epistemically Assisting Freedom

Often a criticism of democratic decision making is that individuals within democracy are not good judges for making democratic decisions. However, some have proposed that increased human augmentation with AI systems would solve this epistemic problem (Fuller, 2018: 3). Already we see this in a minor sense when looking at ‘fact checkers’ on platforms such as X (formerly Twitter). But some have speculated that this may increase in the coming years. Devices such as ‘neuralink’ could provide augmented humans with access to online information which could greatly enhance our ability to make reliably well informed decisions (Gurtner, 2021). Following a similar vein to the fact checking system on X, such a system might be able to provide live fact checking in one’s daily life and give one access to a wealth of information previously unavailable. However, relying on such a technology would pose serious issues, and it has been argued that the development and mechanisms of this technology should be sufficiently transparent to the public (Fourneter, 2020: 671).

We might also be able to enhance our intellectual abilities through technology, giving us access to large amounts of data, making us more informed and therefore ‘freer’ as our actions would be more likely to adhere to our desires, and our desires more likely to adhere to our interests (Susskind, 2018: 167). However, what could be perceived as an enhancement on freedom, could equally be seen as a form of manipulation when we consider where the information comes from, and who has presented it (Susskind, 2018: 167). Suggestions of maintaining ‘cerebral hygiene’ to prevent bias and manipulation seem counterintuitive in the context of public political deliberation as we may become incredibly uninformed on many important issues (Griffiths, 1997: 130; Haac, 2018).

Some have also suggested that the influence of others only becomes manipulative when it offers no opportunity for an individual to reflect on or discuss the information (Susskind, 2018: 171; Sunstein, 2016). If such information does not generate answers, but provides information for you to consider, then the issue of manipulation may be circumvented.

2.5.2 Quality of Information

The intersection of AI and disinformation campaigns in electoral processes has been a focal point in scholarly discourse. Study by Allcott and Gentzkow (2017) shed light on how social media and AI are harnessed to orchestrate and propagate sophisticated disinformation. Advanced algorithms wielded in generating fabricated news articles, deep fake videos, and manipulated images contribute to a disconcerting landscape where discerning truth from falsehood becomes increasingly challenging for users. This manipulation, as underscored by Lazer et al. (2018), not only undermines trust in democratic institutions but also disrupts the foundational principles of informed decision-making within electoral contexts. The proliferation of AI-driven disinformation campaigns underscores the imperative for multifaceted strategies, including technological solutions and media literacy initiatives, to counteract the deleterious effects on democratic processes and restore the integrity of information

dissemination in electoral arenas. Aside from fake news, AI can also more deceptively affect self-rule by shaping information environments, economics of news, speech and manipulation on a structural level, as noted by Jungherr (2023).

Typically in politics prior, what was disputed when we were making decisions was ‘what we ought to do in lieu of the facts’. Now with AI algorithms feeding alternative accounts of the facts to each respective echo chamber, what is now being deliberated is what ‘the facts’ even are (Susskind: 2018: 230). This is harmful for democratic deliberation since deliberation is intended to accommodate reasonable moral disagreement (Gutmann and Thompson, 2004: Ch 1). If person A and B disagree about what the facts of the case are, then any claim of what we ought to do from either party cannot be used until this first disagreement is resolved. Whilst this disagreement about facts may have existed prior to AI-generated content, the sheer volume of alternative facts, and the way they are pushed towards specific user types, presents a further challenge.

Moreover, the participation of AI bots in online discourse can undermine the quality of information. These are AI algorithms that pretend to be people in online spaces. Often this is harmful to deliberation since they spread false information or pretend to forward an extreme ideological position to further exacerbate division (Susskind, 2018: 232). Bots have also been found to target other bots activities in online spaces: thus, in a way deliberation itself is now being automated (Sample, 2017; Tsvetkova et al, 2016).

2.5.3 Diversity of Discourse

Since in the digital world we now live in, public discourse is conducted in online spaces, and these spaces are governed by private companies, this makes digital media companies responsible for several things. First, they can decide what is worth reporting, and what isn’t, thus they can potentially limit the impact of information harmful to their own interest but in the interest of the public (Susskind, 2018: 143). However, the internet also provides a large marketplace from which smaller sources of information can have an impact (Benkler, 2006: 177 – 178). Previously the news was reserved for the mainstream media.

They can also limit what topics can be discussed on their platforms by their users. If left in the hands of private firms then, a severe issue may result in that some political opinions are deliberately withheld, and others are emphasised (Susskind, 2018). In a less overt manner, this could be done by only presenting one particular position in a negative way. This subversion through digital media has been termed by Zittrain et al as ‘digital gerrymandering’ (Zittrain et. al, 2014).

Filtering is also done through search engines: as any given search creates millions of results, the information must be rank ordered (Granka, 2010: 266). As such, the information given to us through these systems – by the method of the systems – determines what we get to know. Even though we have access to other search results, we cannot see them all, nor can we be sure why the first search results were shown. This is a powerful tool to take advantage of. Stewart, Cichocki and McLeod (2022) outline the ways that social media algorithms “sort and target” information, typically based on

likelihood of engagement.³ Moreover, search engine algorithms have been found to ‘push’ a fairly limited range of new sources (Nechushtai and Lewis, 2019).

Firms also have their own financial interests, as such it is not always in their interest to give an equal platform to all users (Susskind, 2018: 193). In this respect, we have two diametrically opposed rights that seem hard to reconcile. If we view platforms as a public good, or in some way linked to the deliberative process of democracy, it stands to reason that each person should have equal access to it as a resource regardless of their views. However, these platforms are privately owned, and therefore they also seemingly reserve the right to refuse service and exclude people from using it.

³ For more on algorithmic targeting and sorting see section 2.2.1 in module D.

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